

Innovative approach to evaluate the significance of the difference in performance between the split and integrated types heat pump water heaters

Stephen Tangwe^{*}, Kanzumba Kusakana.

Abstract:

This paper compared the coefficient of performance (COP) of two residential types of air source heat pump (ASHP) water heaters using statistical tests. The study determined the COPs and the electrical energies consumed, by a 1.2 kW split type and 0.9 kW integrated type ASHP with tank size of 150 L. The COPs were determined after series of the controlled volume of hot water (150, 50 and 100 L) drawn from each tank at different time of use for both the summer and winter seasons. Power meters, flow meters, and temperature sensors were installed on both types of ASHP water heaters to measure the data needed to determine the COPs. The results depict that the mean COP of the split and integrated type ASHP water heaters were 2.965 and 2.652 for the summer and 2.657 and 2.202 for the winter seasons, respectively. In addition, the p-values of the average month-day COPs for the split and integrated type ASHP systems during the winter and summer season was 7.09×10^{-24} and 1.01×10^{-11} , based on the one-way ANOVA and Kruskal-Wallis tests. Furthermore, the multiple comparison test was employed together with one-way ANOVA and Kruskal-Wallis statistics to show that there exists significant difference between piece-wise COPs groups' pairs at 1% significance level among the four COPs groups.

Keywords:

Air source heat pump, Coefficient of performance, one-way ANOVA test, Kruskal-Wallis test, Multiple comparison test, Significant difference, p-value

**Corresponding Author Email:lstphen@cut.ac.za*

I. INTRODUCTION

Hot water heating is responsible for a significant contribution of the monthly electrical energy consumed in the residential sector globally. It can be confirmed that most of the sanitary hot water production in the residential sector is achieved by the operation of poor efficient electric geysers [1]. ASHP water heater is a renewable and efficient technology for sanitary hot water heating and can utilize one unit of electrical energy to produce three units of useful thermal energy to heat water to the set point temperature [2]. The common categories of residential ASHP water heaters are the split and integrated types [3]. It must be emphasized that the COP of ASHP water heaters depends on the design of the components that make up the closed loop circuit of the vapour compression refrigeration cycle, the ambient temperature, the volume of hot water consumed and the thermo-physical properties of the refrigerant [4]. The ASHP water heaters can operate without the assistance of an auxiliary backup element in the ambient temperature between -4 and 40 °C [5]. The COP of an ASHP water heater is better

during the summer relative to the winter period, provided the volume of hot water consumed from both systems are constant. Research conducted with identical split and integrated types of ASHP water heaters without auxiliary element showed that the integrated system performed better than the split type [6]. There is paucity information on testing of existence of significant difference in COPs between two or more types of ASHP water heaters operating under the same conditions. Tangwe (2018), have used the one-way ANOVA test to demonstrate that there exists a significant difference in the COPs of a split and an integrated type ASHP water heater. Both systems were operating under same ambient conditions and the same volume of hot water was drawn off from each tank [1]. The used of statistical tests for comparison of performance of process or quantity is only meaningful, provided the sample data is a true representation of the actual population and the data measurement are unbiased, with a tolerated uncertainty [7]. The study focused on the systematic drawn off of hot water from two identical split and integrated type ASHP water heaters such that 150 L was drawn off in the morning (07:00-10:00); 50 L in the afternoon (13:00-15:00) and 100

L in the evening (17:00-20:00) per day over the monitoring periods. The hot water set point temperature for each of the types of ASHP water heater was 55°C. The systems were switched off before each specific volume of hot water was drawn and was switched on simultaneously to allow for the systems to heat the stored water to its set point temperature. The average COPs for the respective 150, 50 and 100 L, for each of the months of January to December 2018 were determined for the two types of ASHP water heaters. Furthermore, for each of the types of ASHP water heaters, the determined COPs was divided into two groups, namely the summer COPs (January, February, March, April, September, October, November and December) and the winter COPs (May, June, July, August). The one-way ANOVA and the Kruskal-Wallis tests were used to show whether a significant difference exists in the COPs among the type of ASHP water heater and their season (summer or winter season).

II. CALCULATION AND THEORY

COP of the ASHP water heater is the ratio of the useful output thermal energy gained by the stored water to the input electrical energy consumed during the heating cycle, given by Eq. 1.

$$COP = \frac{Q}{E} = \frac{mc(T_2 - T_1)}{pt} \quad (1)$$

Where,

m = mass of water heated by ASHP water heater and was measured by flow meter (F1)

T2 = Temperature of water exiting the outlet of the ASHP unit and was measured by temperature sensor (T2).

T1 = Temperature of water entering the inlet of the ASHP unit and was measured by temperature sensor (T1).

p = Power consumed by the ASHP water heater and was measured by power meter (P1 and P2).

t = Time taken and was measured by the data logger

c = specific heat capacity of water (4.2 kJ/kg/k)

III. STATISTICAL TESTS

A. One-way ANOVA test

The one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) is used to verify if there exist any statistically significant differences between the means of more than two independent groups [8]. Generally, if the confidence level for the one-way ANOVA is assumed as 99%, then the significance level is 0.01. The null hypothesis is rejected when the p-value for the groups is less than or equal to 0.01.

B. Kruskal-Wallis Test

The Kruskal-Wallis test is a nonparametric version of a classical one-way ANOVA. It compares the

medians of the groups of data to determine if the samples come from the same population [9]. The F-statistic used in classical one-way ANOVA is replaced by a Chi-square statistic, and the p-value measures the significance of the Chi-square statistic [9].

IV. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Materials

The list of hot water heating devices, sensors, transducers, and data loggers used in the study is shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Hot water devices and sensors for the setup

Item	Material	Quantity
1	1.2 kW input split type ASHP unit	1
2	3kW ,150 L electric geyser	1
2	0.9 kW, 150 L integrated ASHP water heater with a 0.5 kW back up element	1
3	Flow meters	3
4	Temperature sensors	6
5	Power meters	2
6	Data logger	1
7	Waterproof data logger enclosure	1

B. Experimental setup

The study was conducted under the research and development project of the energy service company called the AET Africa, situated in the factory hub in Dimbasa, in the Eastern Cape province of South Africa. Figs. 1 and 2 show the schematic diagram of the experiment setup. The split type ASHP water heater was formed by retrofitting the electric geyser with the split type ASHP unit and the heating element disabled. Flow meter (F1) was installed in the proximity of the inlet pipe into the split type ASHP unit. Two flow meters (F2 and F3) were installed at the outlet pipes that allowed the hot water drawn off to exit the storage tanks of the split and integrated type ASHP water heaters. The temperature sensors (T4 and T3) were installed at closed range on the pipes to the inlet and outlet of the split type ASHP unit. The temperature sensors (T2 and T1) were installed to the pipes close to the inlet and outlet of the 150 L tank of the split type ASHP water heater. The temperature sensors (T6

and T5) were installed to the pipes close to the inlet and outlet of the tank in the integrated type system. The power meters (P) were installed to measure the power consumed by the split and integrated type ASHP water heaters. All the sensors were configured by Hoboware pro software to log in 5-minute interval throughout the monitoring period and the data were stored in a data logger.

Fig. 1: Installed split ASHP system and sensors

Fig. 2: Installed integrated ASHP system and sensors

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Comparison of the COPs among the four groups

The COPs of the ASHP water heaters were basically classified into four groups (the COPs during the summer season of the split type ASHP (COP_SS), the COPs during the summer season of the integrated type ASHP (COP_SI), the COPs during the winter season of the split type ASHP (COP_WS) and the COPs during the winter season of the integrated type ASHP (COP_WI)). The one-way ANOVA and the Kruskal-Wallis tests were used to test, whether a significant difference exists among the four groups at 99% confidence level and 1% significance level.

i. Comparison of the COPs among the four groups using one-way ANOVA

The data of the COPs among the four groups (COP_SS, COP_SI, COP_WS and COP_WI) are shown in the ANOVA plots in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3: ANOVA plots of the COPs of the four groups

The one-way ANOVA plots showed that the four groups are normally distributed as there are negligible outliers on each plot. The average COP of the four groups (COP_SS, COP_SI, COP_WS and COP_WI) was 2.965, 2.653, 2.658 and 2.205, respectively. The highest average COP was experienced by COP_SS while the lowest was depicted by COP_WI as shown in the red line

(central horizontal line on each ANOVA plots) on each of the ANOVA plots. The upper and lower horizontal black lines on each of the ANOVA plots represented the upper and lower limits of the COPs for each group-means. Table 2 shows the one-way ANOVA table from the distribution of the four groups.

Table 2: One-way ANOVA table for the COPs from the four groups

Source	Sum of square	Degree of freedom	Mean square	F (statistics)	Prob >F
Groups	4.679	3	1.56	91.9	7.0×10^{-24}
Error	1.154	68	0.017		
Total	5.834	71			

It can be deduced from the one-way ANOVA table that the sum of squares between the four groups was 4.679 while the sum of squares within the groups was 1.154. The mean square between the groups is quotient of the sum of squares between the groups and the degree of freedom between the groups and was 1.56 ($4.679/3 = 1.56$). The mean square within the groups is the quotient of the sum of squares within the groups and the degree of freedom within the groups and was 0.017 ($1.154/68 = 0.017$). The F-statistics is the ratio of the mean square between the groups and the mean square within the groups and was 91.9 ($1.56/0.017 = 91.9$). The probability of the F-statistic gives the p-value. The p-value of the four groups was 7.0×10^{-24} and was very smaller than 0.01. Hence, the null hypothesis that, there exists no mean significant difference among the four groups of COPs is rejected. Therefore, there exists a significant difference of the COPs among the four groups at 1% significance level.

ii. ANOVA–multiple comparison algorithm to test for significant difference between pairs, among the four COPs groups

The ANOVA-multiple comparison test used the statistics from the one-way ANOVA to perform a test which verified, if any, significant difference exists between all possible pairs of groups among the four groups. Both difference in the lower and upper 99% confidence levels of the true means between pairs of groups among the four groups are determined. If the difference in the true mean of the

lower confidence level and the difference in the true mean of the upper confidence level of the piece-wise groups’ pairs, are such that the range of the intervals include zero, there will exist no significant difference between the piece-wise groups’ pairs. On the contrary, if the difference in the true means at the lower confidence level and the difference in the true means at the upper confidence level of the piece-wise groups’ pairs are such that, the range between the two confidence levels don’t include zero, significant difference exist between the piece-wise groups pairs.

Fig. 4 depicts that five out of the six groups of piece-wise groups’ pairs (among the four original groups), show significant difference in their COPs. The piece-wise pair of COP_SI and COP_WS, shows no significant difference at the 1% significance level as the difference between the pair with reference to the true mean COPs at the lower confidence level (-0.1259) and that at the upper confidence level (0.116732), do have a zero in the interval of the confidence levels. Alternatively, the p-value between the piece-wise pair of COP_SI and COP_WS was 0.99964 and was greater than 0.01. Hence, the line plots for the COP group-means did overlapped. It can be depicted that the p-values between the rest of the five piece-wise groups’ pairs shown significant differences at the 1% confidence level, as all their p-values are less than the 0.01. More so, the piece-wise pair of COP_SI and COP_WS (represented by horizontal line segments of each group COPs) did overlapped and shows no significant difference.

Fig 4: Groups’ ANOVA- multiple comparison plots

iii. Comparison of the COPs among the four groups using Kruskal-Wallis test

The mean-ranks of the COPs of the four groups (COP_SS, COP_SI, COP_WS and COP_WI) was 58.910, 31.060, 32.450 and 6.580, respectively. Table 2 shows the Kruskal-Wallis table for the distribution derived from the four groups. The Kruskal-Wallis table is similar to the one-way ANOVA table with the exception that the analysis is performed with the mean-ranks of the distribution and not the mean values. In addition, the F statistic in the one-way ANOVA is replaced by the Chi-square in the Kruskal-Wallis table.

It can be observed from the Kruskal-Wallis table that the sum of squares between the four groups in terms of mean-ranks was 23705.9 while the sum of squares within the groups was 7343.1. The Chi-square is the ratio of the mean square between the groups and the mean square within the groups was 54.21 ($7901.95/107.99 = 54.21$). The probability of the Chi-square gives the p-value. The p-value was 1.01×10^{-11} and very smaller than 0.01 significance level. Consequently, there exists a significant difference of the COPs among the four groups at 1% significance level.

Table 3: Kruskal-Wallis ANOVA table for the COPs from the four groups

Source	Sum of square	Degree of freedom	Mean square	Chi-square	Prob- Chi-square
Groups	23705.9	3	7901.95	54.21	1.01×10^{-11}
Error	7343.1	68	107.98		
Total	31049	71			

iv. Kruskal Wallis–multiple comparison algorithm to test for significant difference between pairs of groups among the four COPs groups

The Kruskal-Wallis-multiple comparison test used the statistics from the one-way ANOVA but in terms of mean-ranks to perform the test that check, if any, significant difference exists among three or more groups by testing for significant difference between groups pairs. This is achieved by computing the true mean-ranks of the lower and upper 99% confidence level of each of the groups and then subtracting the

corresponding true mean ranks of the lower and upper 99% confidence level for each between groups pairs among the four groups. If the difference in the true mean-rank of the lower confidence level and the difference in the true mean-rank of the upper confidence level of the between groups pairs, are such that the range of the interval include zero, there exists no significant difference between the groups’ pairs. Furthermore, if the lines of the means-ranks of the piece-wise groups’ pairs on the multiple comparison plots overlapped, it implied, there exists no significant difference between the groups’ pairs among the four groups under investigation. Fig. 5 shows that five out of the six piece-wise groups’ pairs of mean-ranks shows significant difference among the four groups of COPs. The between piece-wise groups’ pair of COP_SI and COP_WS, shows no significant difference at 1% significance level. Alternatively, the p-value between the groups’ pair mean-rank COPs (COP_SI and COP_WS) was 0.997 and was greater than 0.01. The Kruskal-Wallis multiple comparison plots for the four groups depicted that only the between groups’ pair (COP_SI and COP_WS) did overlapped and shows no significant difference.

Fig 5: Groups’ Kruskal-Wallis multiple comparison plots

VI. CONCLUSIONS

The COP_SS demonstrated the best performance while the least performance was exhibited by COP_WI from the analytic and statistical methods. Both tests showed that there exists a significant difference at the 1% significance level among the

four groups of COPs. Furthermore, the ANOVA-multiple comparison tests and the Kruskal-Wallis – multiple comparison tests were used for the COPs groups to show that there exists a significant difference between five out of the six piece-wise groups' pairs (COP_SS and COP_SI, COP_SS and COP_WS, COP_SS and COP_WI, COP_SI and COP_WI and COP_WS and COP_WI) among the four groups. Hence, we can conclude that either of the tests can be used as statistical tools to test for existence of a significant difference among three or more groups.

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Author Biographical Statements

Stephen Tangwe (PhD, CEng, MIMECHE, CMVP) is a postdoctoral research fellow at the department of Electrical, Electronic and Computer Engineering, faculty of Engineering Built Environment and Information Technology, Central University of Technology. He is a Chartered Engineer and a Member of the Institution of Mechanical Engineers (CEng MIMechE) and also a CMVP and an energy expert. He holds a PhD in Engineering from the University of Sunderland in the United Kingdom. He is a seasoned author and reviewer in accredited peer review Journals.

K. Kusakana (DTech, Pr.Eng, and CEM) is a NRF rated researcher. His research interests are power and energy systems, energy management, renewable and alternative energies. He is currently a Professor and Head of the Electrical, Electronic and Computer Engineering Department at CUT. He is a seasoned Author and reviewer in a series of DHET accredited peer review journals and conference proceedings with high impact factors.